

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

M8.1: Concept for users' preferences and recommendations

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M8.1 Concept for users' preferences and recommendations:

The aim of WP8 is to generate specific recommendations for the optimal design of the data and services that the EURHISFIRM RI should provide. Recommendations were developed by gathering and analyzing the preferences of potential end-users and key stakeholders in both academia and industry. This information was gathered via an online questionnaire, which was carried out between October 2018 and January 2019 (D8.2), and also through semi-structured interviews with potential users, which were conducted between June and August 2019 (D.8.3). Following on from these stages, and the completion of the Synthesis Report (D8.4), we make the following specific recommendations for the design of the EURHISFIRM infrastructure:

I. Content

1. We recommend that priority should be given to data relating to the twentieth century, as this was the most popular time period among our respondents.
2. Regarding forms of company data, we recommend that priority should be given to ordinary equity market data, which was by far the most popular with respondents.
3. The EURHISFIRM platform should also aim to provide access to accounting data. Specifically, total assets, total debt, revenues, and profits.
4. Data related to government and corporate bonds should be less of a priority.
5. In terms of frequency of prices, we recommend daily and monthly data, where possible.
6. As regards geography, the United Kingdom was the most popular country, followed by Germany and France.

II. Usability

1. We recommend that the EURHISFIRM platform should enable users to download the data in bulk, in MS Excel format, and with minimum restrictions on downloads per day. We recommend that the EURHIFIRM platform use Wharton Research Data Services as an example of best practice in this area.
2. For reassurance as to the accuracy of data, users should be able to 'click through' to a scan of the original document and EURHISFIRM should provide a full citation of any source material.
3. We also recommend that EURHISFIRM provide an explanation of the methodology and rationale for any interpretation or manipulation of data carried out by EURHISFIRM researchers.
4. For less popular data, we recommend that EURHISFIRM provide simple, non-tabulated PDF scans of the original source document, where possible.
5. It is important that a feedback channel is available for users. An email address would be sufficient.

A more detailed discussion of users' preferences can be found in the D8.4 Synthesis Report.